

The Electron-Ion Collider at Brookhaven National Laboratory

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The Electron-Ion Collider (EIC), designed by a partnership between Brookhaven National Laboratory (BNL) and Thomas Jefferson National Accelerator Facility (TJNAF), will seek to answer how nucleons — neutrons and protons — are assembled to form the nuclei of atoms, and uniquely address three profound questions about them:

- How does the mass of the nucleon arise?
- How does the spin of the nucleon arise?
- What are the emergent properties of dense systems of gluons?

The mission need for the new collider was acknowledged by the U.S. Department of Energy, and CD-0 was granted on December 19, 2019.

The EIC takes advantage of the entire existing Relativistic Heavy Ion Collider (RHIC) facility [1] with only a few modifications at a relatively small cost on the scale of the project. The well-established beam parameters of the present RHIC facility are close to what is required for the highest performance of the EIC, with the exception of the total hadron beam current, which will be increased by a factor of approximately three by increasing the number of bunches. The addition of an electron storage ring (ESR) inside the present RHIC tunnel will provide polarized electron beams up to 18 GeV for collisions with the polarized protons or the heavy ions of RHIC. The EIC design must satisfy the requirements of the science program while having acceptable technical risk, reasonable cost, and a clear path to achieving design performance after a period of initial operations. The present EIC design is the result of a design strategy which takes all these requirements into account. The storage-ring-based design meets or even exceeds the requirements referenced in the 2015 Long Range Plan [2], including the upgraded energy reach:

- Center-of-mass energy (ECM) of 20 to 140 GeV.
- A luminosity of up to $10^{34} \text{ cm}^{-2} \text{ s}^{-1}$ (the Long Range Plan requires 10^{33} to $10^{34} \text{ cm}^{-2} \text{ s}^{-1}$).
- High polarization of electron and light ion beams with arbitrary spin patterns, with time-averaged polarization of $\sim 70\%$, as required by the Long Range Plan.
- Beam divergences at the interaction point and apertures of the interaction region magnets that are compatible with the acceptance requirements of the colliding beam detector.
- Collisions of electrons with a large range of light to heavy ions (protons to uranium ions; the long-range plan requires ions as heavy as uranium).
- Up to two interaction regions.

The RHIC tunnel incorporates two large experimental halls with infrastructure for two major colliding beam detectors. These are at the 6 o'clock position, where the RHIC STAR detector [3] is currently operating, and the 8 o'clock position, home of the RHIC sPHENIX detector [4] (see Figure 1). The design described here supports two EIC detectors, but the project scope includes only one interaction region and one detector. In this report, we describe in detail the interaction region (IR) configuration for a large, general-purpose detector in one of these areas (likely the 6 o'clock area), which fulfills the requirements for the full range of EIC science questions described above. Our plans for the EIC include the capability for two such detectors.

The scientific requirements, calling for high luminosity and near-complete angular coverage by the detector, result in an IR lattice that produces a significant degree of chromaticity (energy sensitivity of the beam optics). The nonlinear sextupole fields needed to compensate for this effect generally limit the dynamic aperture and must be well optimized to provide sufficient beam lifetime. Calculations motivated by experience at HERA [5] indicate that adding an identical, second IR can be achieved without further reduction of the dynamic aperture. We thus plan to allow for detectors at both the IR6 and IR8 positions. The forces acting on the particles in each beam, which are introduced by the collective charges of the opposing beam, respectively, and the corresponding dynamical implications are called beam-beam effects. To avoid unacceptably large beam-beam effects in the case of two experiments, the collider would operate in a mode where each of the two experiments sees half of the bunch crossings; i.e., each experiment receives half of the total luminosity. The highest luminosities can only be achieved by implementing strong cooling of the hadron beams to counteract emittance growth by intrabeam scattering (IBS) [6] associated with the corresponding small beam emittances. Cooling of hadron beams with energies up to 275 GeV requires a novel cooling technique that is being developed and tested in a BNL R&D program [7].

The luminosity is proportional to the electron beam current. At energies of 10 GeV and higher, the electron beam current is limited by the RF power installed to replace the synchrotron radiation power emitted by the electron beam. The installed RF power of 10MW is not a hard limit, but a design choice to limit construction and operations costs.

The design satisfies all requirements without exceeding fundamental beam dynamics limits. In particular, the design parameters remain

Figure 1. Schematic diagram of the EIC layout.

within the limits for maximum beam-beam tune-shift parameters (hadrons: $\xi_p \leq 0.015$; electrons: $\xi_e \leq 0.1$) and space charge parameter (≤ 0.06), as well as beam intensity limitations and IR chromaticity contributions. The EIC is composed of one of the present RHIC superconducting accelerator rings, an ESR with a similar circumference in the same tunnel, and an injector ring for on-energy injection of polarized electron bunches. The hadron and the electron beams collide in one (and possibly two) interaction point(s). The outline for the EIC is shown in Figure 1.

Polarized electron bunches carrying a charge of 7 nC are generated in a state-of-the-art polarized electron source. The beam is then accelerated to 400 MeV by the electron injection LINAC and injected into the rapid cycling synchrotron (RCS) that is also located in the RHIC tunnel. Two batches of four of these 7 nC bunches are injected into adjacent RCS RF buckets and subsequently merged into two 28 nC electron bunches. Once per second, a new electron bunch is accelerated to a beam energy of up to 18 GeV and injected into the ESR, where it is brought into collisions with the hadron beam.

The spin orientation of half of the bunches is anti-parallel to the magnetic guide field. The other half of the bunches have a spin parallel to the guide field in the arcs. Spin polarization in the ESR approaches an equilibrium polarization due to the combination of stochastic depolarization [8] and self-polarization, the Sokolov-Ternov [9] effect. The initial high polarization of 85% of freshly injected electron bunches will decay towards the equilibrium polarization with a time constant of at least 30 min (at the highest energy of 18 GeV). To maintain high spin polarization, each of the bunches with their spins parallel or anti-parallel to the main dipole field is replaced

every one to three minutes depending on the polarization direction with respect to the magnetic guide field. The polarization lifetime is larger at lower beam energies, and bunch replacements are therefore needed less frequently. The highest luminosity of $L = 1 \times 10^{34} \text{ cm}^{-2} \text{ s}^{-1}$ is achieved with 10 GeV electrons colliding with 275 GeV protons ($E_{\text{CM}} = 105 \text{ GeV}$). The high luminosity is achieved due to large beam-beam parameters, at the shape (or large aspect ratio σ_x / σ_y) of the electron and hadron bunches at the collision point, and the large circulating electron and proton beam currents distributed over as many as 1,160 bunches. Table 1 lists the main design parameters for the beam energies with the highest peak luminosity.

At lower center-of-mass energies, the collision parameters must be re-optimized to remain within the limitations already discussed, which tends to result in lower luminosity. At a higher center-of-mass energy, achieved by increasing the electron energy to 18 GeV, the electron beam intensity must be reduced to prevent the synchrotron radiation power loss from exceeding 10 MW. Figure 2 shows the peak luminosity versus center-of-mass energy that will be achieved in the EIC. In the case of collisions between electrons and ions, the electron-nucleon luminosity is lower, but event rates comparable to the electron-proton case are achieved.

The electron and hadron beams must be quickly separated after collisions to avoid parasitic crossings without introducing separator magnets, and to avoid the associated generation of synchrotron radiation in the detector region. The beams therefore collide with a crossing angle of 25 mrad. Collisions with a crossing angle reduce the overlap region of the colliding bunches, which reduces the luminosity by an order of magnitude with 25 mrad. In addition, with

Parameter	Hadron	Electron
Center-of-mass energy [GeV]	104.9	
Energy [GeV]	275	10
Number of bunches	1160	
Particles per bunch [10^{10}]	6.9	17.2
Beam current [A]	1.0	2.5
Horizontal emittance [nm]	11.3	20.0
Vertical emittance [nm]	1.0	1.3
Horizontal β -Function at IP β_x^* [cm]	80	45
Vertical β -Function at IP β_y^* [cm]	7.2	5.6
Horizontal/Vertical fractional betatron tunes	0.305/0.31	0.08/0.06
Horizontal divergence at IP α_x^* [mrad]	0.119	0.211
Vertical divergence at IP α_y^* [mrad]	0.119	0.152
Horizontal beam-beam parameter ξ_x	0.012	0.072
Vertical beam-beam parameter ξ_y	0.012	0.1
IBS growth time longitudinal/horizontal [hr]	2.9/2.0	-
Synchrotron radiation power [MW]	-	9.0
Bunch length [cm]	6	2
Hourglass and crab reduction factor [10]	0.94	
Luminosity [$10^{34} \text{ cm}^{-2} \text{ s}^{-1}$]	1.0	

Table 1. Maximum luminosity parameters.

Figure 2. UEIC electron-proton peak luminosity versus center-of-mass energy (ECM). The luminosity for low ECM is limited by space charge, for intermediate ECM by the beam-beam interaction, and for high ECM by the electron beam intensity and the total synchrotron radiation power. (Solid lines connecting the dots are inserted to guide the eye.)

a crossing angle, the transverse beam-beam forces depend strongly on the longitudinal position of individual particles in the bunch. These forces generate strong synchro-betatron coupling and strong resonances that affect the beam lifetime and stability. These crossing angle effects are avoided by employing crab crossing [11], using crab cavities. Compensation of the crossing angle with crab cavities is a technology routinely demonstrated in the electron-positron collider KEKB [12], and crab cavities are part of the high luminosity upgrade of the LHC. The main elements of the EIC that have to be added to the existing RHIC complex are:

- A low frequency photo-cathode electron source delivering up to 10 nC bunches of polarized electrons at 1 Hz.

- A 400 MeV normal-conducting S-band injector LINAC.
- A 400 MeV to 18 GeV spin-transparent rapid-cycling synchrotron (RCS) in the RHIC tunnel.
- A high-intensity ESR in the RHIC tunnel, with up to 18 GeV beam energy using superconducting RF cavities.
- A high luminosity interaction region with 25 mrad crossing angle, crab cavities, and spin rotators that allows for a full acceptance detector; a second interaction region is possible and feasible.
- A 149 MeV energy recovery LINAC that provides continuous electron beams for strong hadron cooling.
- A small number of additional buildings. The most important ones will house additional RF power stations, pulsed magnet systems, and the electron injector complex.

The ESR design is using established and existing technologies which were previously implemented at high intensity ESRs such as the B-factories of KEK [12] and SLAC [13], as well as at modern synchrotron light sources.

In conclusion, the presented EIC design based on an ESR and its injectors added to the RHIC complex is an attractive, low-risk solution, which meets all requirements on an electron-ion collider at reasonable cost.

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